

The Role of Culture in Education

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Abstract:

Culture is the basic sets of values, opinions and behaviours that are learnt by the members of a society through other members and institutions. It is the network of knowledge manifested by artistic, literary, linguistic and religious practices. Among the several sub-cultural value systems, education, learning and language play very important role in culture. Education plays a great role in the production of a disciplined citizen as well as in the creation of free spirited body. There is an essentiality of education for the process of cultural transmission and vice versa. The preliterate culture witnessed the contribution of education for the preservation indigenous culture. In ancient India and China, students spent a great deal of time in memorizing religious text and manuscripts for the preservation of tradition and culture. Cultural signs and symbols have always structured the human lives through narratives and these have been the basic components of moral education or Virtue Theory. Our present schooling system may fail in terms of proper education when it lacks in concern for learning, truth and culture. So, inculcation of traditional values and culture in the pedagogy, curriculum and assessment will not only enrich the cognitive performances of the students but will also enhance other psychological processes like reasoning, self-motivation etc among them.

Key words: Popular Culture, Moral Education, Virtue Theory, Banking Education

Introduction:

Culture is the set of basic values, perceptions, wants and behaviour learnt by a member of society from family and other institutions. Culture manifests itself through arts, literary forms, music, language, and religious practices (Masterson, & Pickton, 2010, pp100). Culture as the networks of knowledge, consists of learned routines of thinking, feeling, and interaction with other people along with the corpus of substantive assertions and ideas regarding the various aspects of the world. It is the tradition of knowledge is unique in its own way. It is a collection of interconnected individuals who are separated by race, ethnicity, or nationality, mainly transmitted from the older members to the new one and mostly externalized by rich symbols, artifacts, social

constructions, and social institutions like cultural icons, advertisements and news media (Hong, 2009, P4). Thus, media have a deep impact on various elements of human culture. As children grow up, society provides them with a framework within they are able to develop acceptable beliefs, value systems and cultural norms. Within any culture, there will be subcultures. A subculture consists of an association of a group of people with shared value systems based on common life experiences and situations. These shared value systems may be based on ethnic origin, geographical areas and religion (Masterson, & Pickton, 2010, pp100). There are various subcultures, which are the important segments that influence public behaviour. Exhibit1 depicts the various elements of culture influencing the society.

Source- Masterson, R. & Pickton, D. (2010). Marketing: an introduction,, Figure-3.14, pp-100.

Mass media is also known as mass mediated, popular culture or low culture as the popular culture is supported by the idea that it is the mass-produced commercial culture; whereas high culture is the result of an individual act of creation (Storey, 2008, P6). Popular culture in the form of mediated texts such as films, music, comic books, television, etc influences the knowledge of the people like children and adults. Popular culture texts are often utilized as part of people's leisure activities. They are generally texts that are used for entertainment or amusement. People including students consume these mediated texts. Some view the texts as harmless, others view them as an important factor for upholding the society's cultural and moral values. Educators often consider popular culture texts as a tool of education. Ideological messages are communicated through representations, thus mass media becomes an important tool for education. Some believe educators should acknowledge popular culture or mass media as the important site for learning as they could link between the school and college-based education system to the learner's everyday lives and experiences. Popular culture often reflects the youth culture, school culture and local culture. So media literacy i.e. teaching about the power of textual representation for both the teachers and learners has been an important factor in any culture (Esposito, & Banks, 2009, pp 601-605). Apart from Media, various other elements such as language, gender, food, technology, law etc are the important sub-cultural elements. Education, language and learning are also vital elements for any culture. Ethnolinguistic inquiries rely on two grand approaches in defining the relationship between language and culture. At first, language depends on culture and secondly, language organises culture (Jourdan, & Tuite, 2006, P 5).

The fundamental purposes of education are to determine the characters of everything else. These can be the curriculum, pedagogy, and assessment. Education can have more than one aim. The aim can be to produce a law abiding citizen, at the same time to produce a free spirit who can question any proposal which he/she encounters. The major educational aims are concerned both with the needs of the society and with the needs of the individuals. The individual needs are mainly concerned about the individuals' security

over their cultural background, whereas the social needs are apprehensive about the preservation of society's culture. Both Instrumental, Intrinsic and Liberal aims of the education are to preserve the culture of the society (Winch & Gingell, 2008, pp9-50)

Teaching and Learning Culture

Durkheim (1956) has claimed education as the process of cultural transmission. But it is surprising that there is a little in the literature regarding the role of culture in any educational package. The concept of education has three separate meanings: a) all the beliefs and practices of a given society; b) the intellectual and artistic beliefs and practices of a given society; and c) the best intellectual and artistic beliefs of a given society. Most of the literature deals with relationship between the intellectual and artistic beliefs along with the best beliefs of a given society, neglecting all three meanings of the culture at a time.

The essentiality for education runs deeply among the adult community. In the preliterate cultures, the elders of the community mainly educated its youth for the survival and existence. Thus, these members contributed to their indigenous culture and became the main part of their culture. This type of education was gender specific. Girls were taught to cook, sew, take care of their children and family, and to perform all kinds of domestic chores. Boys were mainly indulged into the outdoor activities such as hunting, tilling fields, looking after the livestock, training with the weapons, trading and learning craftsmanship from their ancestors. They learnt about their history and values through different forms of art such as legends, stories, dances and songs. They also learnt about the harsh condition of lives and various strategies of survival through cooperation and co-works.

The early education system existed to teach the children and youths about the norms, values and proper behaviour of the culture. In ancient China, students were drilled to learn the philosophical teachings of Confucius. In ancient India too, students were engaged in learning the verses from the ancient Vedic texts and scriptures. Generally, students spent a deal of time in memorising the religious texts and oral traditions of the ancient Hindu culture (Bogucki, 2008, pp375-377). Students' learning and conduct are largely affected by difference in values in a

cultural system. These differences affect the students' personal independence, competition, ambition, social harmony, and attitude towards authority. Culture in United States has a deep preference for individual approach towards the life in achieving success. Western culture supports independence, competition and focus in objective among the learners while attaining the goal of success. Learners with the origins in culture of East Asia have preferences towards the conformity and harmony over individualism and personal achievements. Some cultures expect teachers and professors to have an expertise over the subject, while other recognises that teachers may not know all the answers regarding any topic of their subject. Other supports teachers' full and final authority over the learners and the learning environment, while others see them just as mentors. Students from cultures that teach respect for the wisdom of their elders may be reluctant to share their opinions, their disagreement with the readings, or their challenges towards the teaching in or outside the classrooms. Some culture value memorisation as a critical component of learning and the learners from such culture can get confused when they are suggested to dismiss memorization and to adopt analysis, synthesis and critical evaluation in learning (Davis, 2009, pp59-62).

Apart from the traditional and customary culture, each school or institution develops its own culture. School culture is particularly helpful in supporting, indentifying and creating a framework for occupational learning. Each school organisation has different mindset about the school life (Stoll & Fink, 1996, pp 82-83). For educators, expressions of purpose are plentiful. Education is not only concerned about equipping children with the knowledge of occupational skills, but aid in respecting others cultures and beliefs, developing an appreciation of the richness of one's own cultural heritage and of the spiritual and moral dimensions to life (Gardner, Cairns, & Lawton, 2000, pp 150-152).

The famous activist educator John Dewey (1859 -1952) advocates teacher to be more concerned about thinking, reflection, democratic ideals, and community values. Actions must be linked with certain values in teaching and learning process. There must be a more interactive and experiential approach

in teaching and learning (Powers-Costello, 2009 P 16). The Brazilian educator, Paulo Freire (1921-1997) emphasised on technical and functional adult education and literacy for social and cultural transformation. It is highly essential to embrace adult education for social transformation in order to understand the way the dominant culture works and this can be the basis for transforming the oppressive conditions in which adult learners and their families and communities live. Freire always stressed the topic of culture. In the culture circle, adult learners are assisted to understand that culture is created by people, and that people like themselves are able to change those cultural elements, which are harmful to themselves (Torres, 2009, pp 18-20).

Freire's texts *Pedagogy of the Oppressed* (1970) and *Cultural Action for Freedom* (1972), referred to the term 'banking education' where knowledge is literally deposited in learner's mind. This banking model of knowledge leads to domination of facts and ideas into the learner's mind. So, it is essential that learners must be critically literate and for this learning should not only represent technical skills but development of a critical social and cultural awareness. Teachers must adopt teaching method that will promote critical thinking skills among the learners. There must an encouragement of the disciplining of mind towards the thinking which involves reflexivity, skepticism, and a holistic approach to both the teaching and learning process. Teachers in the elementary schools may begin to move the learners beyond rote memorization and fragmentation of facts by providing them with opportunities to appreciate their own cultural diversities. At the postsecondary level, college and university professors must actively engage the students in processes that demand for the evaluation of the knowledge (McCrink, & Melton, 2009, P 206). For example, in a college media science course, students may be asked to read different articles and raise their voice regarding current burning issue like homosexuality and the way traditional Indian culture accept or condemn it.

Moral Education and Culture

Human lives are structured by narratives, which must be realised and equipped by humans to form the basic components of moral education or Virtue Theory. Virtue

theorists describe children can be educated about moral character and cultural values initially through the process of training and then subsequently, through reflective practices. Virtues are the desirable characteristics such as kindness, fairness or courage that every culture wants to develop and cultivate in their societal bodies through moral education (MacIntyre, 1981). Moral education in opposition to the moral indoctrination cannot be conducted without treating the students as the rational human beings are capable of reasoning about conduct. Such reasonable atmosphere can be created by creating a class culture i.e. a community based on enquiry within the class premises, where children can learn the social forms of reasoning and mutual respect. Through participation in the community, pupils will be able to learn how to reason along with the cultivation of social habits. Such participation is highly essential for the good moral conduct within the class culture. Good class culture along with the community of enquiry can contribute both to the value based educational programmes as well as in the development of language and thinking skills. Thus, it will facilitate students' fully fledged participation in a pluralistic society and cultural community. In a caring classroom culture, children can learn to develop their personal concern about love, death, friendship, bullying, fairness, and other general philosophical issues like personal cultural identity, meanings and values (Gardner, Cairns, & Lawton, 2000, pp 49-51).

Failure in Curriculum and Minority Culture Education

Our present schooling system fails in terms of proper education as it lacks concern for beauty, truth, learning, and culture (Goodman, 1964). Culture has a wide range of influences on the cognitive performances of the students. It has innumerable avenues for influencing psychological processing by the members of a certain culture. Most of the obvious influences are performed through languages and communication processes. There are two broad aspects of linguistic influences on human psychology. At first, cultures have concepts that are discussed habitually. These forms of cultural expertise are transformed from one member to another and thus, affect the reasoning process of the member. Secondly, the languages on which

emphases are made, they are different in the information, thus it is quite evident that the language with which these members speak and the way they think are totally different in nature (Markman, Grimm, & Kim, 2009, pp94-95). Language, thought and culture (Salzmann, Stanlaw, & Adachi, 2012, P225) are deeply interlocked. Teachers have to understand the relationship with an adequate knowledge about the society. The language includes two dimensions. At first the accessive one, which involves a new manner of disclosure of what in a sense already exists. The second dimension includes the existential i.e. a new manner of being or a new possibility. The descriptive language fits in the first dimension while expressive gesture makes up the second. For defining the manliness of term bike-rider, expressive words like macho and dude are used. Such differentiation among the two dimensions is influenced by the distinctions like lovers/ friends, or leader/president/king and such distinctions are not same from culture to culture (Taylor, 2006, pp 29-38). In current configuration of school curricula, the teachers (primarily first and second-language), are mainly responsible for developing linguistic abilities of the students. Teachers must not neglect these distinctions in dimensional space of language. They must be alert looking for the opportunities in order to extend and develop the student's linguistic skills for the promotion of independent learning by the students. As the language opens up the reach rather than restricting the opportunities for learning, implementation of local and indigenous language and cultural signs and symbols can help in learning processes. Learning experienced through own languages can promote personal development, and idiosyncratic expression, thus opening up the new paths for cognitive or affective horizons (Moore, 2000, pp 62-65).

Heath (1983) uses ethnographic research technique to investigate the proper cultural styles and practices suitable for children of two communities i.e. Roadville and Trackton. These two communities were only few miles apart in the Piedmont Carolinas. Roadville was the white working class community engaged in textile mill for more than four generation whereas Trackton was the black working class community whose older generation grew up in the farm lands, but

then present generation was working in the textile mill. Heath examines the impact of cultural mismatches on both children of the communities. His study draws attention towards the cultural, class and ethnic differences, which facilitates the children of the dominant white community over the ethnic minority one. The cultural symbols in terms of spoken and written language such as literary and non-literary works hardly favoured the minority group (pp 2-67).

The revised curriculum published by the Consultation Material May-June 1999 too limited the opportunities for curriculum innovation in education Action Zone. A thorough content review of the curriculum has stated the aims namely: to provide opportunities for all pupils to learn and to achieve and; to prepare all pupils for opportunities, responsibilities and experiences of life are missing. The revised curriculum mainly sets out to define more sharply the processes in which schools and pupils must participate if all pupils are to receive their entitled best achievements and establishing a flexible and coherent framework which can readily and quickly meet all pupils' needs. Though both the processes are important, still the revised curriculum failed to provide comfortable homes for the teachers and pupils of minority cultures (Gardner, Cairns, & Lawton, 2000, pp 7-11). Cognitive skills such as critical thinking and problem solving are important for the learners as attitude and motivation play a great role in cognitive thinking. A teacher must have enough knowledge about the model of cognitive skill to enhance the academic affordability for the learners in the classroom (Phye, 1997, pp64-65). The motivational state of the students is also influenced by the culture to which they belong. The differences in culture encourage them to hold on their individualist values or collective values. The average members of western culture tend to hold on their primacy as the individual whereas the students of the East Asian culture central around their collective identities (Markman, Grimm, & Kim, 2009, pp94-96) and collaborative learning environments (Davis, 2009, P274). Motivation can be negative or positive. Teachers as the mentors can provoke resistance among the learners through threats and power assertion. They can also generate positive motivation through

warmth, reciprocity and stimulation of empathy towards other's culture. Empathy as the element of motivation can contribute to the moral and ethical values as it focuses on other's feelings and how one's action affects other life (Howell, 2009, pp516-517). Most students' response positively to a well-organised course taught by an enthusiastic teacher or instructor who shows a genuine interest in students and their learning process. Thus, it promotes and enhances students' motivation (Davis, 2009, P279).

Conclusion

Several studies suggest the best source of gaining knowledge that students can gather is by openly sharing the ignorance and expressing a genuine curiosity to learn from different groups and culture. The do-it-yourself culture in learning process has ignored the traditional methods for authenticating knowledge and designating authority as it promotes personal choices and opinions over expertise and authority. Primary, secondary and senior- secondary educational institutions can promote cultural studies by organising personal development programs such as workshops and conferences, ethnic film festivals, and cultural tours; visiting museums and heritage places and ; forming of book reading groups to study both fiction and non-fictional literatures from different cultures. A teacher has to adopt several pedagogical approaches to avoid misinterpretations among the students from diverse backgrounds. Teachers must learn the differences in communication styles and non-verbal behaviours of different cultures. There are certain differences in communication techniques such as nodding, eye contact, physical contact, smiling, pauses after the speech, physical distance, and usage of languages, which varies from culture to culture. Culture as the reflection of our basic values, perceptions, desires and behaviours, is widely manifested through various artistic and literary form of expression. So, learning process must collaborate with such manifestation.

Culture has a deep connection with its various subcultures such as media, language, and education along with the process of learning. As education is the road to culture, it aims at civilizing the powerless and underprivileged one. Culture and language have deep relationship. There is a significant

relationship between the both in mutual determination, mental representation and social action. Friedrich (1969) defines the term 'linguaculture' that serves the fact that culture is a part of language just as language is a part of culture. These two are partly overlapping realities, which can intersect in many ways (P 219). Some learners are naturally enthusiastic about learning, while others may require continuous instruction to be inspired, stimulated and challenged in the learning process. The level of motivation can transform the classroom into a better or worse place of learning. Alternative testing modes such as open-book test may reduce some student's motivation to study as in many cultures memorization is still considered as the best way to study.

The movement of deschooling supports Goodman's principle that our present schooling system fails to impart proper education when it lacks concern regarding moral and ethical values, truth, beauty, learning and culture. Some believes our present schooling system is required to be removed and replaced by other system that can improve the possibility of societal and cultural progress. Both cultural studies and evolution are widely recognised not only in arts and philosophy but also in science, politics, and government and in all other social and mental phenomena. All cultures in preliterate era including the Paleolithic age have some artistic and aesthetic responsiveness. The study of culture requires proper planning and prudence. Learning and motivation are seen as important form of social activities that can be understood within a given cultural setting. So, inculcation of traditional values and culture in the pedagogy, curriculum and assessment will not only enrich the cognitive performances of the students but will also enhance other psychological processes like reasoning, self-motivation, critical thinking, etc among them.

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